

SHORT NOTES

THE SAPOGENIN FROM SEEDS OF *ACHYRANTHES ASPERA* LINN

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In a previous communication (Khastgir and Sengupta, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 529), we have described the isolation of a triterpene acid, oleanolic acid, from the roots of *Achyranthes aspera* Linn. Gopalachari and Dhar (*J. Sci. Ind. Res.*, 1952, 11B, 209) isolated a saponin in 2% yield from the defatted seeds of the same shrub, and on acid hydrolysis of the saponin, obtained a sapogenin, m.p. 305-306° (acetate, m.p. 293-300°; 3:5-dinitrobenzoate, m.p. 290-91°) to which they assigned the molecular formula, $C_{20}H_{46}O$.

We have isolated a crude sapogenin fraction from the seeds of *A. aspera* and separated it into three fractions: (a) neutral, (b) acid, potassium salt of which is sparingly soluble in water and (c) acid, potassium salt of which is soluble in water. The neutral fraction (a) on repeated chromatography over alumina did not yield any crystalline material. The acid fraction (b) yielded oleanolic acid in 1.1% yield, which was characterised through its acetate, methyl ester and methyl ester acetate. The acid fraction (c) did not yield any crystalline acid.

Procedure.—The crude sapogenin, obtained in the same manner, as described in our previous communication (*loc. cit.*), from dried and powdered seeds (500 g.) was filtered, dried and extracted in a Soxhlet apparatus with ether for 6 hours. The ether solution was washed with 3% aqueous potassium hydroxide solution, when a flocculent precipitate was obtained. The water layer was filtered after separation from the ether layer.

The ether layer was washed with water until neutral, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated, when 0.85 g. of a gummy neutral material was obtained. On chromatography over activated alumina (50 g.), almost the entire material (0.81 g.) was eluted with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°) as a gum, from which no crystalline solid could be isolated even after repeated chromatography.

The aqueous alkaline solution, after the separation of the sparingly soluble potassium salt, was acidified and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated, when 0.52 g. of a dark tarry mass was obtained, which resisted all attempts at crystallisation.

The sparingly soluble potassium salt was acidified with cold and dilute HCl and extracted with ether. The ether solution was washed with water, dried over anhydrous sodium sulphate and evaporated, when 6.1 g. of a crystalline acid, m.p. 292-300°, was obtained.

Oleanolic Acid.—The above acid on crystallisation from a mixture of chloroform and methanol gave colorless crystals of oleanolic acid, m.p. 303-305°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 79^\circ$ (CHCl_3), (5.6 g., 1.1% on the basis of dried seeds).

Oleanolic Acid Acetate.—The acetate was prepared in the usual manner with acetic anhydride and pyridine. On crystallisation from acetone, it melted at 262-65°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 77.5^\circ$ (CHCl_3). The mixed m.p. of the acetate with an authentic specimen of oleanolic acid acetate did not show any depression.

Methyl Oleanolate.—The acid on treatment with an ethereal solution of diazomethane gave methyl oleanolate, which after crystallisation from acetone gave colorless crystals, m.p. 197-98°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 77^\circ$ (CHCl_3).

Methyl Oleanolate Acetate.—The above ester on acetylation with acetic anhydride and pyridine gave methyl oleanolate acetate, which after crystallisation from acetone gave colorless crystals, m.p. 215-16°, $[\alpha]_D^{25} + 71^\circ$ (CHCl_3). The mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of methyl oleanolate acetate did not show any depression. (Found: C, 77.71; H, 10.00. Calc. for $\text{C}_{33}\text{H}_{52}\text{O}_4$: C, 77.29; H, 10.22%).

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